

Council on

Library

Resources

Inc.

1ST ANNUAL REPORT

for the period ending june 30, 1957

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• SEPTEMBER 1956—NOVEMBER 1957

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COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent non-profit body incorporated in 1956 in the District of Columbia, having as its principal objective "to aid in the solution of library problems; to conduct research in, develop and demonstrate new techniques and methods and to disseminate through any means the results thereof." The Council was established at the instance of the Ford Foundation which has made it a grant of \$5 million to be expended over a five-year period.

The Council, whose members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C. It proposes to carry out most of its work through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals.

the

FIRST YEAR

The Council came into being on September 18, 1956, the date of its first meeting. This, the report of its activity for the fiscal year ended June 30, 1957, covers in consequence a period somewhat longer than nine months.

During this period the Council completed its housekeeping arrangements, made progress in defining its program, reviewed a large number of proposals for the support of a wide variety of activities, and made a number of grants.

“THE PROBLEMS OF LIBRARIES”

The general objective expressed in the Council's corporate charter is further specified by the terms of the Ford Foundation grant. This was made “for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally, and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and providing leadership in, and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives.”

What, then, are these "problems of libraries" to which the Council's activities are directed?

In the 1880's, when Andrew Carnegie commenced the munificences which were to result in the erection of nearly 3,000 library buildings before his death in 1919, the outstanding problem of libraries was to get them established. Even in the United States, in spite of general acceptance of the principle of publicly supported education, the greater part of the population was at that time without convenient access to library facilities.

As against fewer than 4,000 libraries in the United States in 1885 (the year in which Andrew Carnegie gave \$500,000 to establish a public library in Pittsburgh), there are in the country today nearly 13,000 libraries and library systems. (Many of these systems comprehend scores, hundreds and even in some cases thousands of component libraries; for example, Harvard's 45 libraries, or the thousands maintained by the Armed Services.) Libraries are recognized as necessary not only to research and higher education but to education at all levels (there are estimated, for example, to be some 20,000 school libraries), to business and industry, to the conduct of public affairs and the satisfaction of individual needs.

Thus, while the establishment as well as the maintenance of libraries will continue to require large sums from both public and private sources, yet the problem of establishment no longer has the primacy it once possessed.

To many, the outstanding contemporary problem of libraries would rather appear as one simply of improving and extending present facilities through the application of known techniques. There are indeed few libraries which do not need, for the better execution of their tasks, improved or larger buildings, more extensive collections, greater capacity for analysis through cataloging and indexing, more branch libraries or bookmobiles, larger and more expert staffs, and so on. In general, however, these are recognized as local problems.

But the improvement and extension of library service cannot be achieved exclusively by local developments. The services which libraries give are to a large degree dependent upon the products and services of others. This dependence commences with the book-announcement and book-reviewing media on which the librarian's selection of books is based; it continues to rest upon the quality of the books procured, upon the indexing and other bibliographic services by which readers can be guided to books of particular use, upon arrangements which facilitate identification of needed books and access to them, wherever they may be. Paradoxically, the greater a library, the greater is its dependence upon services obtained from outside the walls. Librarians have consequently been impelled, in many situations, to join efforts for supplying needed services for which commercial sources were lacking.

If full advantage could be taken of known techniques and methods, the quality of library service would undoubtedly be greatly improved, and the ultimate consumer—the library user—would undoubtedly be enormously benefited. We know how to stimulate the production of books to provide information in better form than do existing books; how to create and organize additional indexing and other bibliographic services; how to develop guides to library resources so as to assure access to materials even though unavailable locally; how to assemble through microcopying or publishing projects the resources for research now scattered through the libraries and archives of the world so that almost any library might supply in compact form the materials which would otherwise take lifetimes of travel and sifting to discover.

But to take full advantage of such possibilities would involve costs which neither libraries unaided nor the community on their behalf are prepared to pay. Especially is this the case since the first costs of such services are not the last: it is characteristic of bibliographic tasks that they require to be done over

and over again from time to time. Thus, the index to the literature of just one field of study (chemistry) costs over \$1 million annually to publish, and libraries generally must pay an annual subscription of \$350 in order to make it available to their customers. It would seem unlikely that similar arrangements could be successfully applied to the literatures of all the other subjects where it might be desirable. Thus again, in 1927 the first edition of the *Union List of Serials* (the principal record of the files of periodicals and other serial publications held by American libraries, and an almost indispensable tool for purposes of identification, acquisition and location) cost \$58,000 defrayed from contributions of \$1,200 each by forty libraries and a grant of \$10,000 from a foundation. In 1957, by contrast, it is estimated that a third edition, badly needed, would cost in excess of \$2 million. Still again, the archives of Europe were ransacked several decades ago at a cost exceeding a half-million dollars to bring together in this country photocopies of the most important documents for American history. This was a magnificent achievement. It is now desirable to apply similar techniques for the benefit of many other studies. But does this not ultimately involve the copying of the major masses of archival and other material in the world, merely to rearrange the copies elsewhere around new foci of interest?

Libraries will—indeed must—continue to encourage by purchase and often by other forms of assistance the production of materials and services by which they can better serve the needs of their readers (and ultimately the aims of scholarship, good government, good citizenship and the good life); they will continue to supply through cooperative effort services for which commercial sources are wanting or unsuited. But sooner or later for each library comes a point at which it can no longer afford to subscribe to additional bibliographical services or participate in further cooperative ventures. The fact is that, even now, libraries are unable to take full advantage of available services.

But suppose that the facts were otherwise. Suppose that each library could expand its collections and catalogs to the ultimate of its aspirations. Suppose that it could fill its reference rooms with the innumerable special indexes, abstracting services and digests—all kept up to date with regular cumulations and supplements—which would be required to analyze all published (and perhaps all unpublished) literature from the innumerable points of view from which information is sought. Suppose that it could, as the result of microcopying and other projects, provide its readers with the resources for scholarly research from all places and all times. Is it not likely that under these seemingly ideal circumstances the conduct of research in libraries would be smothered (as it almost is today) by plethora and complexity?

In summary, the fact is that even if unlimited funds were available, we could not with present techniques solve the essential problems of libraries. Even if cures were limitlessly applied in terms of present knowledge, the result would probably only be a further glutting of the channels of communication.

THE FOLGER LIBRARY CONFERENCES

For several years the Trustees of the Ford Foundation made inquiry regarding the problems of libraries and the possibilities of solving them. As part of this inquiry, the Foundation requested Dr. Louis B. Wright, the Director of the Folger Shakespeare Library in Washington, as the chairman of a committee

which included as its other members Dr. Leonard Carmichael, the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution, and Mr. L. Quincy Mumford, the Librarian of Congress, to convene a group to discuss these problems. Two meetings were held at the Folger Shakespeare Library on January 15 and March 31, 1955. In the first were assembled some 50 representatives of many professions concerned with libraries, either as users of library collections, or as administrators of organizations embodying libraries, or as librarians. This group freely explored various approaches to the problems of libraries. Many suggestions resulted: for acquiring fuller knowledge of library resources now available and for using this knowledge to coordinate the collecting programs of libraries; for planning programs of preservation of deteriorating materials and of relocation of little used materials so as to assure maximum usefulness; and for the exploitation of scientific aids to learning. Perhaps the central conclusion of the discussion was that libraries, though suffering from all the effects of a machine age, have gained disproportionately little benefit from it; that because libraries do not in many cases provide a market large enough to stimulate the supply of special equipment for their particular needs, many potentially applicable developments in science and technology have not been brought to library tasks. At the second meeting, on March 31, a smaller group, including some of the participants in the earlier meeting, considered what action might be taken to improve the situation, and agreed unanimously that what was needed was a planning body, quite independent of other organizations and free to attack the various problems of libraries.

The final recommendations, signed on behalf of the group by Dr. Wright, were submitted to the Ford Foundation on April 9, 1955, together with two studies of possibilities for action, one by Dr. Ralph R. Shaw of the Graduate School of Library Service, Rutgers University, the other by Dr. Herman H. Fussler, Director of the University Library, University of Chicago.

THE COUNCIL'S PROGRAM

The action taken by the Ford Foundation embodied the essentials of the recommendations of the Folger Library Conferences. The Council is a planning, not an operating body, and is wholly independent of other groups working in the library field. Its membership of twelve is representative of the public interest in libraries rather than of the interest of any class of library users or of the libraries themselves. Nevertheless, within its membership may be found not only the point of view of the users of libraries for research both in the humanities and in the sciences, but also the points of view of the administrators of educational and research organizations of which libraries are a part, of library administrators, and of completely detached interest in the processes of communication.

The Council has freedom to range widely through research and development in all fields to determine new attacks upon the traditional problems involved in the storage and dissemination of knowledge, to enhance and accelerate the development of libraries generally through the encouragement of new methods and assistance in coordinating their application, the promotion of interlibrary cooperation, the pooling of the reservoirs of little-used material in the interest of greater availability, and the coordination of library work even across national boundaries. High on the Council's list of priorities, it is the hope of the Foundation, will be basic research which may lead to new developments.

In a field of endeavor which has received unremitting attention for more than three quarters of a century from an organized and self-critical profession, not deficient in ingenuity or cooperativeness, such an assignment is not an easy one. As might

perhaps have been expected, the Council has found it much easier, during the early months of its existence, to recognize the kinds of activities that do not come within its scope than to announce projects of outstanding promise. Yet certain areas may be marked out within which it may be expected that opportunities for fruitful work will be found:

Basic research in the processes of distribution, organization, storage and communication of knowledge as these affect libraries.

Technological development looking to the physical-mechanical apparatus of library work (including the collections themselves) and to the application of mechanisms not yet utilized.

Methodological development and coordination of effort looking to over-all improvement. Most areas of library work are susceptible of such development: acquisition, bibliographic organization (including cataloging, indexing, etc.), storage, and access both to collections and services. Under this topic would also be included the possibilities for integration of the processes of publication, distribution, bibliographic organization and storage so as to bring the library function more automatically and effectively into the publication-storage-research-publication cycle.

Emphasis upon these areas of activity implies certain exclusions from the scope of the program. The Council's purpose is to develop solutions to library problems in general rather than in particularized or local terms. It cannot, accordingly, undertake to relieve the problems of individual libraries by providing funds for "normal" purposes—the construction of buildings, procurement of collections, or strengthening of staffs. This restriction must ordinarily also apply to projects of cataloging and classification, even though such projects may often seem to their originators as exceeding "normal" activities; yet circumstances may be envisaged in which the organization of a particular body

of material might be so important for the needs of scholarship as to justify the Council's interest.

The hope of finding general rather than particular solutions, and of stimulating improvements in method rather than the mere application of existing techniques, must also weigh in the Council's attitude to certain other classes of activity. There are, for example, almost inexhaustible opportunities for useful work of a bibliographic nature—for the compilation of surveys of the literature of this or that subject or of guides to the resources for studying them, for the preparation of indexes and catalogs of many kinds and in many forms (including union catalogs and lists), for specialist listings in aid of particular studies, etc. Notwithstanding their potential usefulness, the Council's interest in such projects must be guided either by the degree to which they promise a wide-spread and general assistance to the usefulness of libraries or by their potential effectiveness in demonstrating methodological improvement. Similar considerations must also affect the support of the many possible and undeniably important programs for reassembling by photocopy the materials for study which are now dissipated in many repositories or otherwise difficult of access, so as to make them widely available for research. These are, in a sense, publication projects, and libraries after all owe their *raison d'être* to publication. It might in consequence eventually appear that no greater contribution to the usefulness of libraries can be made than by promoting publications of basic or "source" value to the maximum, by photocopy as by other means. But for the present at least the Council's support of publication projects, whether by photocopy of manuscript originals or by microcopy of works already printed, must depend upon considerations of methodology as well as the usual criteria of intrinsic importance, desirability of dissemination, need for preservation, etc.

BASIC RESEARCH

Because libraries constitute but one link, as it were, in the communication chain, it is almost impossible to consider them or their problems separately from those of other parts of the sequence. It is partly, at least, for this reason that it is so difficult to understand what has happened to libraries at a point in their history at which they should be—and indeed are—flourishing as never before, but at which their own sense of insufficiency, and that of their users regarding them, is also at a height.

For one thing, as intermediate organisms, libraries have little or no control over the circumstances which principally determine the facts of their existence. They do not control what books are published, or even what kind of paper these books are printed on; nor, on the other hand, can they dictate the uses that will be made of these books when organized into collections. Theirs is essentially the function of a filing system.

A library could once be simple—a mere collection of books with a rudimentary inventory thereof; but this was at a time when the other parts of the communication process were simple also. What has happened to libraries is essentially the result of what has happened in the other parts of the process.

Now, what has happened to the communication process generally is that during the very period in which the quantity of publication has been increasing at fantastic rates, the interests of research have concentrated on progressively smaller units of information within publications. Thus we have an ascending curve of analysis constructed on an ascending curve of publication.

The situation is apparent for all to see. It has frequently been described, usually with the use of such epithets as “deluge,” “inundation,” “flood,” “quagmire” and “avalanche,” in attempts to suggest the appalling quantities of printed materials which our

civilization produces—quantities so great that, rather than facilitate the availability of information, which was the purpose of publication, they threaten to conceal or even to lose it.

As an example, in the field of medicine in 1880 approximately 20,000 articles appeared in some 800 medical journals. The figures today represent an almost ten-fold multiplication: some 200,000 articles in some 7,000 medical journals. The Royal Society of London recorded only 1,555 scientific journals for the whole of the 19th century; for less than half the 20th, the *World List of Scientific Periodicals* lists 50,000. The most careful estimates of world-wide publication arrive at a figure of somewhat more than 550,000 titles (not including separate issues of newspapers, periodicals, etc.) a year; but since the Library of Congress alone receives approximately 5,000,000 pieces a year, there is little doubt that this is a grave underestimate.

Meanwhile, the individual inquirer tends to be more and more interested in details, and more and more minute indexing and analysis are consequently required. *Chemical Abstracts* in 1907 used an average of 3.5 index entries per article; in 1956 it used approximately 12.5; and cases have occurred where more than a thousand entries have been used to analyse a single article. A similar phenomenon appears in other fields. A center for Byzantine study must index every artifact mentioned in long series of journals on Byzantine art and history; certain philosophical and philological studies require an index to every word written by St. Thomas Aquinas. Instances of this kind could be multiplied indefinitely.

Nor is this all. The number of indexing and abstracting services, all analysing the literatures of various subjects or portions of subjects from various points of view and with much redundancy, has increased at a rate perhaps even greater than that of publications generally: the *Index Bibliographicus* lists some 3,400 of them, among which no fewer than 450 serve the field of medicine alone.

But while proliferation of publication and increasing intensity of analysis have characterized much of the communication process which affects libraries, older needs and patterns have persisted: the specialized periodical article has not displaced the monograph or the general work, or been itself displaced by the unpublished research report. Meanwhile, too, the increasingly urgent need in all intellectual activity for up-to-date information has produced its own useful but voluminous, costly, hard-to-handle and all-too-ephemeral paraphernalia. In one field alone, that of Anglo-American law, there are some 250 current loose-leaf services which have to be maintained by daily interfiling and replacement.

The situation for the user is epitomized by a dialogue occurring at a recent meeting on the forthcoming decennial index to *Chemical Abstracts*. To the horrified question, "What am I going to do with a 19-volume index?" came the answer, "What are you going to do without it?"

Libraries have traditionally organized their collections and services around the book—the monograph—as the unit, but the techniques which have proved adequate for books cannot be efficiently applied to collections which are increasingly composed of smaller units; and the larger and presumably better the library, the more difficult does it become in many cases to find the object of a search. From the reader's point of view there are too many items to be examined, too many finding tools; a lack of a comprehensible and straight-line method for narrowing down a search; overly-great differences in the methods of search for different kinds of information; deficiencies in analysis which give him generalities when he is looking for particulars, or minutiae when he is looking for a general treatment; deficiencies in terminology which condemn him to searching for modern subjects under outmoded nomenclatures; and an exasperating slowness in service, especially when local resources are deficient and those of other libraries must be enlisted. And he might well ask why

he has to go to the library in the first place; it should be possible to secure much of its stored information without moving from his desk or his laboratory.

From the point of view of the librarian the dissatisfaction with the situation would consist of the same elements as those of the reader but would be expressed somewhat differently. To him, too, the multiplicity of materials is dismaying, but in addition to the difficulties of learning about the existence of particular books, of selecting, acquiring and organizing them, there are the difficulties resulting from the lack of planning in their production and in assuring his readers access to such as his library has not itself acquired. So also with the finding media (bibliographies, indexes, etc.): the librarian complains of their number, their planlessness on an over-all basis, their enormous duplication yet enormous gaps, their lack of specific adaptation to the contents of his own collections, and their high cost of purchase and of maintenance.

In what, with respect to such problems, does basic research consist? Does it consist in studies of the habits of library-users with a view to differentiating kinds of readers and their reactions in different physical, bibliographical and topic-of-research circumstances? Or in measuring and evaluating the use made of various library materials through analysis of the published results of current research? Or in controlled experiments duplicating actual research to ascertain how it might have been improved? Or in statistical analyses looking to the more effective selection, arrangement and organization of collections? Or in tests of the bibliographic apparatus for adequacy of coverage, of refinement or generality of analysis, and of terminology; for duplication and gaps, for efficiency in internal organization or in use with particular collections or in use for particular searches? Or in comparative studies of the efficiency of library service under varying circumstances of administration, space-arrangement, institutional interdependence, etc.?

Such inquiries might have useful results, yet are hardly basic; they all assume the major features of present library practice. Genuinely basic research in library problems should probably discard all assumptions derived from present library organization; it might develop models of the intrinsic operations of the research process in the presence of various factors; might ascertain the contributive rôles of informational sources of one kind or another and of the physical and intellectual apparatus associated with each; might explore the psychological processes of analysis and organization as reflected in the structure of the various disciplines and in the work of librarians and of the users of libraries; might eventually engage in linguistic, semasiological and mathematical inquiries in search of the fundamental processes of transmission and exchange of information. Upon such inquiries it is easy to believe that the fantastic capacities of the giant electronic computers for manipulating complex data may well be brought to bear. But, even further, it is not difficult to conceive that the ability of these machines to simulate certain intellectual processes at speeds enormously greater than those of human minds may be brought some day to the intellectual operations, such as cataloging and indexing, which are now the real bottlenecks of library work.

It can properly be remarked that such inquiries go beyond the activities performed in libraries into those of antecedent and subsequent parts of the information process. But this is not necessarily an objection. Library work has in times past contributed the physical form of the book, and more recently the card index and the microprint card to the instrumentation of research; it has contributed to the techniques of bibliography and taxonomy; and it may have other contributions in store.

The Council early considered the possibilities for basic research in library problems. A necessary preliminary step appeared to be a listing of the problems and a survey of the present state of knowledge regarding them in order to permit a selection of topics offering promise to investigation.

"Targets for Research in Library Work"

An inquiry intended to provide just this kind of information was offered by Prof. Ralph R. Shaw of the Graduate School of Library Service of Rutgers University, and the Council has made a grant to the University for the purpose. The study, entitled "Targets for Research in Library Work," will summarize, by means of a team of experts drawn from many institutions, the "state of the art" and the lacunae of understanding in various aspects of librarianship, drawing for the purpose not only from the published literature but also from unpublished evidences of practice. Each expert's findings and recommendations will be submitted to intensive discussion by a group of experts convened for the purpose. The study is being conducted with the advisory assistance of a group which includes not only librarians but also library-problem-minded persons drawn from natural science, scientific instrumentation and business-machine work. Its term is two years but, in view of the Council's need for its results, it is hoped that it may be brought to a termination earlier.

TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT

Perhaps even more than other arts dealing with things of the mind, library work is dependent upon its physical apparatus. It is difficult for an Occidental to conceive of library work as even possible without the arbitrary sequence of the alphabet, or for an American librarian to comprehend that such work can be conducted without the card catalog. A large library in these

days is replete with mechanisms—for moving materials in bulk or in piece; for copying, composing, duplicating and marking; for numerous operations of binding, mounting, laminating and fumigating; for the service of materials by optical and acoustical means; for book-charging, accounting and other business operations; for communication in various forms.

Yet there are many deficiencies in the equipment. Library trustees are usually horrified to learn that bookstack capacities are in the order of 1.5 volumes per cubic foot, but they are less conscious of the costs to library work arising from deterioration of paper, of the waste which occurs from lack of standard requirements for furniture, of the inefficiency of all book-copying devices, and of the frequency of manual operations which would undoubtedly—if library work were a competitive profit-and-loss operation—have long ago given place to mechanisms.

Not only because of the lack of the profit-and-loss statement and because of the tradition of manual operation which persists from the smaller library units into the larger, but also because libraries form a comparatively small market, many potentially applicable devices are not made available for their special uses, including marking and stamping equipment, optical and photographic apparatus, data processing machines, etc.

Another aspect of the situation is the lack of standards or of methods for enforcing them. Though paper is the stuff of the principal commodity purchased by librarians, it is probably safe to say that no librarian as such could identify a standard of color, weight, flexibility, folding strength, ability to accept particular binding and rebinding treatment, and chemical stability to which his suppliers of paper products should be held. For microfilm, where the dangers of deterioration are even greater, because less easily detectable and more devastating than for paper, the complete standard for manufacture, processing and storage is scattered through half-a-dozen standards of several standardizing bodies, and a principal standard is still unpub-

lished. But there are still fewer safeguards or guidelines than this for most of the commodities purchased by libraries.

Yet in those cases in which the library world has been able to assure a steady and profitable market and has entered into discussions with the suppliers, good results have been obtained: witness the standards and trade practices which enable libraries in this country to get good book-binding services.

The Council has considered how it might assist in these matters. It has tentatively reached the conclusion that two lines are open for development. One of these is toward the provision of a general testing-standardizing service for the materials, equipment, apparatus and systems used by libraries. Such a service might be expected to pay for itself in the sense that benefits would accrue to its users, but some difficulties may be foreseen in converting these benefits into cash support for an expensive operation. These difficulties are now being explored.

The other avenue is toward the development of specific apparatus applicable to the particular uses of libraries and toward application of devices used in other activities but not yet brought to library work.

"Deterioration of Book-Stock—Causes and Remedies"

While pursuing the development of arrangements for a general testing-standardizing service, the Council has taken advantage of the life-long enthusiasm of an outstanding documents-restoration expert to commence study toward the betterment of the situation regarding the librarian's chief stock-in-trade—paper. Mr. William J. Barrow, the documents-restorer of the Virginia State Library, an expert in the history and technology of inks and papers and the inventor of an internationally adopted system of document-preservation, has long planned a systematic investigation into paper-deterioration on the hypothesis that this deterioration is due to causes which can be obviated in manufacture or arrested following manufacture at costs much less than

those of any present process of document preservation (including crêpelining, laminating or photocopying). The Council has provided for the support of Mr. Barrow's investigation for 18 months under the sponsorship of the Virginia State Library, whose librarian, Mr. Randolph W. Church, has designated two advisory committees, one of librarians concerned with paper-preservation, the other of experts in the chemistry and technology involved. It is hoped that this study may not only produce data which may contribute to development of standards for library paper-stock but may also provide an economically feasible technique for halting or delaying the deterioration of present stocks and perhaps even an improved method of manufacture.

"Closed-Circuit TV in a Decentralized Library Situation"

Telefacsimile has been in use in newspaper work for more than 30 years and is today a commonplace of the communication of meteorological, cartographic and pictorial information. It has never been successfully applied in libraries: it is too slow (about one page a minute) over the economically feasible band-width provided by a telephone line; and, besides, a book cannot be wrapped around a cylinder for scanning like a photograph or weather map, but must be held in an inefficient cradle. Telefacsimile can not in consequence compete at present with the inter-library loan of a book or with a microcopy of a journal article sent by air mail.

Yet it may be foreseen that if telefacsimile were technologically and economically feasible for libraries, it might considerably alter some of their practices and improve their efficiency. It is true that librarians (and their readers) depend upon the resources of other institutions made available by interlibrary loan and photocopy. But the administration of these services, which involves identification and location of the item sought, correspondence, insurance, receipts and dispatches, charges in and out, payments and collections, etc., is tedious, frustrating

and costly. The dependency which requires interlibrary borrowing is to be avoided if at all possible. Thus, it is better to acquire, whenever it is available, the extensive back file of a journal, even if of little prospective use, rather than to be condemned for the indefinite future to negotiating loans or photocopies. But if an almost instantaneous telefacsimile were available, a whole new series of habits of interdependency might form around it, leading to a much more rational disposition and use of resources.

Until its speed can be sufficiently increased without undue cost, facsimile for libraries is out of the question and is some years away. Meanwhile, however, something can be done looking to its application when available.

In every decentralized library system there are numerous works or sets of books which it is desirable to make available at several service points, yet undesirable to acquire in multiple copies. (This, in microcosm, is the nation-wide situation also.) Lacking telefacsimile, can we derive from a closed-circuit television installation the advantages—economic, sociological and technological—which facsimile would provide, or can we learn from such an installation lessons applicable later?

It is the purpose of a project sponsored by the University of Virginia under the direction of its librarian, Mr. John Cook Wyllie, to explore these questions. The Council has made a grant to the University for a 13-month inquiry into the applicability of closed-circuit TV in an installation between its central and several of its departmental libraries. This inquiry will evaluate the adequacy of existing equipment for the special purpose of televising book material; and it will investigate ancillary equipment such as page-turners. It will attempt to assess, too, certain other factors, such as costs of equipment and of the special arrangements for service at the transmitting end; the acceptability and effect of the service at the receiving end; specifications and tolerances for equipment; and effectiveness toward reducing the number of sets of publications required to be held by the various libraries on the campus.

METHODOLOGICAL IMPROVEMENT AND COORDINATION OF EFFORTS

There is in all human affairs an interesting relationship between man and the machines which he creates to extend his capacities. In extreme cases, this relationship sometimes seems to involve a reversal of the normal rôles of master and servant, and man is found in bondage to his own creature. But even short of these extreme cases, there is no doubt that human attitudes, purposes and behavior are profoundly affected by the mechanisms which he has devised. To take an immediate example, witness the book, a mechanical substitute for and extension of the human memory. What changes it has wrought in human behavior and purpose!

So, too, in library work, there is a relation between objective, method and apparatus which is not well understood. To what extent are the objectives of library work controlled by its methods, and these in turn by the apparatus at its disposal? How might the objectives change if the work were liberated from methodological and instrumental restrictions?

These are interesting if speculative questions. Meanwhile, we know enough of the matter to be able to perceive, for example, that although stated objectives purport to control library work in such matters as bibliographic organization (cataloging, indexing, etc.), yet it is the capacity of the methods which really control the objectives. Similarly, until union catalogs, union lists, photocopying services and interlibrary lending became gen-

eral, librarians could not claim the ability and therefore did not claim the function of making available to their readers the total resources of a region, or of a country, much less of the world. Or, to take a still third example, the utility of union catalogs is at the present time very much limited, not only by the technical difficulties of maintenance and of use, but even more by the modesty of their objectives—and these in turn are controlled by technical considerations.

Method and objective go hand-in-hand in other matters also; e.g., with respect to the rôle which the libraries of educational institutions can play in the instructional process, and in the encouragement of student interest in books. Should effective techniques be found in such areas, the library's conscious objectives might readily accept the additional functions, just as services for adult education have been widely adopted in public libraries, to the extent that effective methods have been found.

The Council is, accordingly, interested to assist toward liberating the objectives of libraries through improvement of their methods equally with the development of the apparatus and equipment which so often affect and control these methods. In pursuing this interest the Council has been brought to remark that the methods of library work are essentially bibliographical, and that these require for their execution, perhaps more than do the methods of other kinds of work, joint efforts in their execution. Library work in its modern pattern would be impossible without the jointly contrived and supported apparatus of codes, classification schemes, indexes, catalogs, cataloging services, etc., by which the work performed in one place is made generally useful, and by which jobs can be done which it would be impossible for individual libraries to execute unaided.

Without underestimating the importance of joint action by librarians in other matters (such as recruiting, education, relations with governmental bodies, etc.), it is consequently toward joint efforts in bibliographic method that the Council's attention

has been particularly directed. It may be expected that improvements here can be brought to bear upon such matters as the planning of acquisitions so as to give assurance (rather than merely hope) that all important parts of the record will somewhere be accessible; upon the organization of this material so that its existence and location may easily (and not only with difficulty) be known; upon the readier service of these materials by techniques perhaps still to be devised. More immediately, a principal problem of many libraries would be met if more effective central cataloging services were available. Relief could be given to many libraries, especially of the smaller educational institutions, if services for more discriminative book-selection and acquisition were provided, for these institutions with their small staffs must now select from the same immense total as do the large libraries with their numerous and specialist competences.

Several considerations have led the Council to proceed deliberately in its search for situations in which it might assist toward improvement of method. One of these relates to the inexhaustible possibilities for bibliographic work to which allusion has previously been made. Another arises from the fact that the most useful bibliographical projects are extremely expensive. It would seem, in consequence, that the best angle of attack in these cases is from the point of view of technological development, with the aim of bringing mechanical aids to the assistance and—it may be hoped—to the reduction of costs of such projects. Also, if methods are to be useful for joint efforts, they must be themselves developed by joint effort. The Council has wished to be sure that those points of view which are essential to success have been consulted. But mobilization of opinion is time-consuming.

“Toward an International Cataloging Code”

The large countries have in the past been for the most part bibliographically self-sufficient, or nearly so, and variations in

national practice have on the whole been unimportant. Even so, there have been attempts to obtain international conformity, especially where common languages obtained. Thus the Anglo-American cataloging rules of 1908 provided a common practice for the English-speaking world; the Prussian Instructions of 1886 have wide acceptance in Central Europe; and the International Federation for Documentation, the International Federation of Library Associations, the International Standards Organization and Unesco (like its predecessor organization under the League of Nations)—representing to a considerable degree the needs of the smaller and less self-sufficient countries—have been pecking away at the matter of uniformity of bibliographic practice for years.

In our increasingly “one world” international uniformity acquires increasing actual and potential importance. There is an increasing amount of international interchange of information between bibliographic services, most observable (because most consciously organized) in the field of science, but important in other fields also. Meanwhile, the librarians of each country are still condemned to cataloging afresh those publications of every other country which they acquire, as though the country of origin were not already doing the job, and possibly better.

In 1941 American librarians partly revised their cataloging code, with unsatisfactory results. After a considerable period of inquiry and discussion, revision is again under way, involving a more fundamental approach than the 1941 effort. As in 1908 it is proposed to involve other English-speaking countries. Just at this time revisionist movements have developed in France and in the countries using the Prussian Instructions. The International Federation of Library Associations has again been exploring the bases for reconciliation of international differences. In the past, the Anglo-American and the Prussian systems seemed so widely at variance in certain important particulars as to offer no hope of this. Genuine improvement suddenly appears possible.

Last May, at a time inconvenient for its own fiscal planning, the American Library Association learned of the opportunity for promoting the idea of an international catalog code that would be afforded by the meeting of the Verein Deutscher Bibliothekare at Lübeck the following month. The Council, which had already been considering what might be done to forward such a code, made the Association a travel grant to assure its representation at Lübeck through the attendance of Dr. Andrew D. Osborn of the Harvard College Library. The step was opportune, for in addition to West German librarians, there were 70 librarians in attendance from East Germany as well as representatives from 9 other European countries, including officers of the International Federation of Library Associations. The hopes for an international code were given substantial support, and not in words only: before the end of the meeting the Verein's cataloging committee voted to abandon the traditional "grammatical" order of filing prescribed by the Prussian Instructions in favor of the "mechanical" method used in French- and English-speaking countries.

CONCLUSION

The Council concludes its first year's operation with the confirmed conviction that, for a field of activity as diverse and complex yet as socially important as library work, a detached point of view and ability to plan, whether exercised by the Council or some other body, is important. The Council's principal concern is to be able to select, from the great number of potential objects of support, those which genuinely contain the promise of improvement. It has been encouraged, stimulated and

helped by a great many librarians and others to whom it is indebted for much time and energy expended on behalf of its program, and without whose interest, sympathy and assistance no program would be possible. The Council enters its second year with many interesting possibilities before it.

VERNER W. CLAPP
President

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

ACCOUNTANT'S CERTIFICATE

August 16, 1957

*To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.*

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements present fairly the assets, liabilities and the fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1957 and its income and grants and expenses for the period from inception, May 17, 1956, to June 30, 1957 in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles. Our examination of such statements was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards, and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

STATEMENT OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES AND
FUND BALANCE

June 30, 1957

Assets

Cash		\$ 256,150
U. S. Government Treasury Bills, due September, 1957 at cost		99,177
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation (see note, page 34)		4,500,000
Airline and utility deposits		450
		4,855,777
		4,855,777

Liabilities and Fund Balance

Grants payable, per accompanying statement		\$ 120,500
Accounts payable and accrued salaries		4,614
Reserve for appropriation approved by Board of Directors		5,000
Fund balance:		
Excess of income over grants and expenses, per accompanying statement	\$4,730,663	
Reserve for appropriation approved by Board of Directors	5,000	4,725,663
		4,855,777
		4,855,777

STATEMENT OF INCOME, GRANTS AND EXPENSES

For the Period from Inception, May 17, 1956, to June 30, 1957

Income:

Grant from The Ford Foundation (see note, page 34)	\$5,000,000
Interest on temporary investments	3,878
	5,003,878

Grants and Expenses:

Grants awarded, per accompanying statement	\$192,400	
General administrative expenses—		
Compensation and employee benefits	50,622	
Rent	4,596	
Legal fees	2,586	
Furniture and equipment	8,327	
Travel and meetings	5,393	
Supplies, printing, insurance, communications and other	9,291	273,215
Excess of income over grants awarded and expenses		4,730,663

STATEMENT OF GRANTS

Year Ended June 30, 1957

	<u>Grants Awarded</u>	<u>Payments</u>	<u>Grants Payable June 30, 1957</u>
The American Library Association Toward international standardi- zation of cataloging—to assist ALA to participate in meeting of German Library Associa- tion, Lübeck, Germany	\$ 1,400	\$ 1,400	
Rutgers University, Graduate School of Library Service Targets for Research in Library Work	100,000	12,500	\$ 87,500
Virginia State Library Deterioration of Book-Stock— Causes and Remedies	49,500	16,500	33,000
University of Virginia Closed Circuit TV in a Decen- tralized Library Situation	41,500	41,500	
	192,400	71,900	120,500

NOTE TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

The Council was established to conduct research in the problems of libraries and to disseminate by any means the results thereof. It received a grant of \$5,000,000 from The Ford Foundation payable over a five-year period. Payments received under the grant prior to June 30, 1957 amounted to \$500,000 and it is anticipated that the Council will require \$750,000 in the second year and \$1,250,000 annually during the three succeeding years.

The terms of the grant from The Ford Foundation provide, among other things, that "the Council shall conduct its operations within and subject to the provisions of its Certificate of Incorporation and Section 501(c)(3) of the Federal Internal Revenue Code, as it may be amended from time to time, so as to maintain its tax exempt status thereunder." Although a definitive ruling from the Commissioner of Internal Revenue confirming tax exempt status has not yet been obtained, in the opinion of legal counsel for the corporation, it should have no difficulty in obtaining such a ruling after the required time has elapsed to permit the Commissioner to appraise the nature of its operations.

